

Herding cats — how to get biologists to preprint

Managing academics is like herding cats. However, funding agencies — if they wish to — have the power to herd the academic cats and drive them to embrace open science and early sharing of research findings through preprints.

. . .

It's often said that managing scientists is like herding cats. But, herding cats is no problem. Just put the food bowl in one corner and they'll all go there.

How to herd cats, euuh, scientists.

Could this cat herding strategy be the solution to the lingering reluctance of biologists to preprint? It may very well be. For years, I thought that Plan U—funders preprint mandates—is the one and only solution to get biologists to preprint. I remain at loss as to why funding agencies—despite all that talk about open science—don't require preprinting from their awardees. But, I have to admit that the Howard Hughes Medical Institute (HHMI) may have come up with a more elegant solution.

Plan U was articulated in this 2019 PLOS Biology article by Richard Sever, Mike Eisen, and John Inglis.

HHMI is one of the most prestigious funders of biological and medical research. The Institute founded in 1953 by the eccentric business magnate Howard Hughes sits on an endowment of over \$20 billion. HHMI's Investigator Program supports hundreds of scientists to the tune of about \$1 million per year. This is as good as it gets for US life scientists. The awards are often greeted with much fanfare and announced through celebratory press releases by the Investigator's host institution. Even plant biologists have benefited from the largesse of the HHMI Investigator Program. In 2011, HHMI teamed up with the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation (BMGF) to fund fifteen plant scientists, a first that was welcomed as incredibly exciting news for this traditionally under-funded community. "Plant Biologists Hit a \$75 Million Jackpot," wrote Science Magazine.

Since 2011, plant scientists have benefited from the HHMI Investigator Program.

HHMI continues to lead and innovate. As neurobiologist and HHMI Vice President Leslie Vosshall announced in a rousing Twitter thread posted in October 2022, HHMI made exciting changes to the 2024 Investigator Competition. With these changes, HHMI expects applicants to demonstrate through their track record a commitment to open science, DEI (diversity, equity and inclusion), and inclusive mentoring. The message is loud and clear. If you wish to become an HHMI Investigator, you will need to describe what actions you have taken towards building a progressive research culture and demonstrate a firm commitment to open science.

Leslie Vosshall PhD

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[@HHMINEWS](#) Open Science: tell us about your specific lab practices that support or promote early and/or open sharing of research results, tools, or materials. (Examples may include use of preprints, publishing in open access journals, submissions to public databases, etc) 3/8

Leslie Vosshall PhD

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[@HHMINEWS](#) cares about open science. We ask you to describe 5 scientific contributions,

What stood out from Vosshall's epic tweets was the emphasis on preprinting as a major indicator of a commitment to open science. Indeed, the preprint movement is known as ASAPbio—reflecting the fact that preprints enable sharing new research and methods faster than traditional forms of publishing. Vosshall wrote that applicants will need to describe “specific lab practices that support early and/or open sharing of research results, tools or materials.” The applicant's scientific contributions will need to be supported by “up to 4 articles—published or deposited in @biorxivpreprint or @medrxivpreprint.”

It reads like applicants will need to have preprinted their best work to stand a chance. If true, then HHMI would have devised a more subtle way to lure biologists into preprinting than the decidedly brutal Plan U mandate. By expecting applicants to demonstrate a commitment to open science in order to be competitive for the Investigator Awards, HHMI has essentially moved the food bowl to the preprint corner to herd the reluctant academic cats. Hurrah!

ASAPbio
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Join the Keynote Speakers: Erin O'Shea (@HHMINEWS), Ron Vale (@HHMIJanelia) Fiona Watt (@EMBO) and @fraser_lab (@UCSF) who will discuss why we need #preprint review and feedback.

Register to watch the livestream on Dec.1-2:
buff.ly/3G0fpfz
[#RecognizingPreprintReview](#)

#RecognizingPreprintReview

I'm writing this post as I'm heading to HHMI Janelia Farm for the #RecognizingPreprintReview Meeting, co-organized by ASAPbio, EMBO and HHMI. These progressive institutions are taking the lead into fully integrating preprints in the life sciences publishing ecosystem. Why not capture open peer-review of preprints in a format that that academic community can recognize. As stated, the goals of this meeting are "to promote community consensus and support for preprint peer review and to create funder, institutional, and journal policies that recognize both preprints with reviews, and reviews of preprints."

We, academics, are infamous for cherishing our independence. We don't like to be told what to do, and most of my colleagues cringe at funder mandates like Plan U even if they agree with its spirit. We are under the illusion that we operate in academia with full freedom. Is it true? Or is this an illusion of choice—the belief that we have more control over our lives than we actually do? Our academic traditions have been shaped by the intense competition for funding and the conflicts of interest inherent to the peer-review system. Our behavior is not the product of free choice but the result of the many variations of the Academic Prisoner's Dilemma games we play. As a colleague told me a few years ago when I asked them about preprints, "I grew up learning how to play the publishing game and now you want to change the rules".

Why biologists don't post preprints?

- **The Old schooler**
 - "I grew up learning how to play the publishing game and now you want to change the rules?"
 - "Preprints don't fit in the games I play with Editors and reviewers."
- **The Metrics Maniac**
 - "My publishing decisions are driven by Journal Impact Factors."
 - "Preprints don't have an impact factor."
 - "I only need papers to get a job/promotion. Preprints don't count."
- **The Paranoiac**
 - "I want to get this paper in a CNS journal, and I want to stack as many chips on my side as I can. Preprints won't help my chances."
 - "I'm convinced preprints would hurt my chances to get in a CNS journal."
- **The Insecure**
 - "I'm never that sure about the first version of my papers and I don't want the world to see it."
 - "Reviewers always improve my papers. I only want people to read the better version."
 - "What if my paper is flawed?"
- **The Libertarian**
 - "I don't like preprints. I don't want anyone to tell me what to do."
- **The Unenlightened**
 - "I don't know what preprints are."
 - "I heard of them but I'm not really sure what it's all about."
- **The Cynic**
 - "It's another fad and it will blow away."
 - "I don't expect anyone would bother to give me feedback on my preprint."

Why biologists don't post preprints.

Let's see how the HHMI experiment pans out. It will be straightforward to evaluate the degree to which the preprinting habits of HHMI Investigators will evolve. Hopefully, the concept that grant applicants must provide documented evidence of their commitment to open science—via preprinting and/or other concrete actions—spreads to other science funders (hello UK Research & Innovation (UKRI), anyone listening?).

I would love to see Plan U widely implemented by funders. But if that's too much for the freedom-seeking academic kitties, then let's give the HHMI model a chance. After all, managing academics is herding cats, not taming tigers.

Some cats may look like tigers, but they're much easier to herd.